

TRADITIONS AND INNOVATIONS OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN TOURISM MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: *The article offers ways to overcome the problems that arise in various tourism activities in Uzbekistan and recommendation for the future, ideas and recommendation Such as concretization of staff responsibilities, and study of new sources of income.*

Keywords: *Tourism, Pilgrimage Tourism, Infrastructure, Pilgrimage, Further development of tourism, Attention to tourism in our country.*

Tourism is one of the fastest growing and most profitable industries in the world economy is one of the leading industries. In recent years, tourism has become a global export has made a huge contribution to the world's gross domestic, product 15%. In particular, the achievements in Uzbekistan on the ground economy liberalization deepen the country modernization of all sector Sustainable development of tourism, one of the leading industries, is also underway. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev noted: "Uzbekistan convenient country for both travel and visiting. Because the whole of our motherland our world –famous ancestors are immortal. They are the rich spiritual and cultural heritage left by him is of great interest in the international area. To further develop the industry, first of all, it is necessary to improve the infrastructure condition.

In our country pays special attention to the further development of pilgrimage tourism and these noble goals are embodied. In the last 2 years in Uzbekistan tourists visiting the holy shrines are also religious from abroad and the number of pilgrims increased significantly. In 2022 the number of foreigners visiting the Republic of Uzbekistan compared to 2021 is 2/3 times.

Pilgrimage tourism is an integral part of modern tourism. There are more than one and a half billion Muslims in the world. That's it half of the Muslims have collected authentic hadiths, making them the second most trusted religion in Islam to visit the khokims of Imam Bukhari, the creator of the source We all know that it will have a positive impact on our economy. In our country the infrastructure to receive so many

visitors has not yet been formed. Religious, historical and cultural monuments visit a particular region or city important to order.

In France it was under state protection about 60 percent of the monuments are also tourist religious sites. The development of general interest in religious tourism in Uzbekistan go back to ancient history. I am proud to say that the world to civilization, to science, to humanity in general, both spiritual and material the history of our ancestors, who made an invaluable contribution to its development, is generous to us bestowed: every inch of our land is sacred, every inch of our land is a shrine. Great our ancestors shared the dreams and aspirations of our people, their strength and scope of thinking. reflects the spiritual world, taste, attitude and culture, depending on their intellect and intellect, the world reckons with us, evaluates us will give.

First of all, it should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan not enough attention was paid to tourism until indence. Objective information and advertising about the tourist potential of the republic not at all. Tourism, service and entertainment infrastructure underdeveloped, low level of tourist services, the world there were almost no contacts with leading tourism enterprises. Conclusion Instead, tourism is one of the most lucrative industries today recognized as one. In this regard, tourism is considered by many countries A number of development programs are being developed.

In the field of tourism, our esteemed president is also paying very attention, in order to accelerate the work on the organization of pilgrimage tourism on November 21 this year, representatives of the Committee on Religious Affairs, the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan, the Center for Islamic Civilization, Tashkent Islamic University and the leading tourism companies in the country held a working meeting.

Chairman of the Committee for Religious Affairs O.Yusupov opened the meeting and said that during his visit to Samarkand region on November 9-10 this year, President Sh. stressed that assignments had been given to the authorities. He also noted that work has begun to develop an action plan to attract foreign tourists to visit Samarkand and Bukhara regions, including the formation of working groups to work with Turkey, Malaysia, Indonesia and other Islamic countries. In his speech, O. Yusupov explained in detail the importance of developing a program to promote the tourism potential of Samarkand and Bukhara regions abroad, including the visit of Imam Bukhari in Samarkand region, Bahauddin Naqshband in Bukhara region. Akmal Kasimov, a specialist of the Asia Tour travel agency, spoke at the meeting. to organize seminars and conferences with the participation of foreign religious leaders, to develop cooperation between Islamic institutions, to participate in grand competitions of influential Islamic organizations.

The speakers also spoke about the Committee on Religious Affairs, the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan, Tashkent Islamic University, the Center for Islamic Civilization, the Charitable Foundation for the Preservation and Improvement of Holy Places and Uzbektourism. offered to sign a memorandum of cooperation. In addition, the preparation of handouts, booklets, banners, reference books and slides for the organization of promotional activities to attract tourists in the field of pilgrimage to the holy sites of the Republic of Uzbekistan, close cooperation with religious scholars in the field of pilgrimage tourism In order to do so, opinions were expressed on the involvement of local scribes with experience in this field, and on measures to be taken as soon as possible to obtain exit and entry visas.

Our country the tourism sector also has great potential to increase its economic potential. Mainly the work being done to develop international tourism will become one of the leading industries in our country.

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In 2017, about 2.7 million tourists visited Uzbekistan. Most of them are probably coming for purposes such as seeing relatives, treatment, study or business.

In order to increase the number of tourists visiting our country today, to acquaint them with the attractiveness of our republic, region and city in general, it is expedient for each of us to serve the development of the industry, first of all.

Used literature

1. Murodjon Mirzayev, Mahbuba Aliyeva “Basic of toursim” textbook, T; 2015 year
2. <http://old.uzbektourism.uz/uz/uzbekiston/-development-prospects-and-the-plase-of-youth-in-it>